

Applied Neural Network for Navy Marine Gas Turbine Stall Algorithm Development

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Abstract—In June 2005^{1,2}, Naval Surface Warfare Center (NSWC) Gas Turbine Emerging Technologies conducted testing on a General Electric LM2500 gas turbine engine. This engine is the main propulsor for DDG-51 and CG-47 class United States Navy surface ships. The purpose of this testing was to induce compressor stall in order to evaluate existing algorithms for stall prediction and gather data for further algorithm development. In addition to existing sensor data, dynamic pressure sensors, with data rates ranging from 20-1000 KHz, were installed in various compressor stages for additional capability.

Utilizing the data collected, in conjunction with a MATLAB-based neural network approach, NSWC has developed algorithms to detect and trend stall margin and related quantities that can eventually be used in an early stall warning system onboard ship. Algorithms can be incorporated into the recently installed Full Authority Digital Control, allowing real-time stall detection and prevention.

This paper discusses the feasibility of employing a neural network approach to detect and output a compressor stall margin value and associated risk of compressor stall for U.S. Navy LM2500 gas turbine engines

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1. INTRODUCTION

In June, 2005, Naval Surface Warfare Center Gas Turbine Emerging Technologies conducted land-based testing on a General Electric LM2500 gas turbine engine. The purpose

of this testing was to collect data to develop algorithms which detect and prevent imminent compressor stall.

For this test, the engine, which employs variable stator vane geometry, was operated at various set points throughout its operating range while stator vane angle was varied from on-design to eventual stall induction. Data was collected and subsequently analyzed.

2. METHODOLOGY

Compressor Map Modeling

During testing, which was conducted at the Philadelphia Land Based Engineering Site (LBES), data was collected at fixed gas turbine generator speeds (N_{gg}) while variable stator vane (VSV) angle was varied manually. Interim vane angle data was collected prior to the actual compressor stall events. This data set is labeled “Map” data.

The effect of increasing vane angle for a given N_{gg} causes pressure ratio, Pr, for the overall compressor (and each individual compressor stage) and consequently translates the operating point along the line of constant speed toward the surge line, as shown on the compressor map in Figure 1 below. In this manner, the gas turbine compressor was stalled at both low speed for stalls 1, 2 and 3 (7000, 7500 and 7800 respectively) and high speed for stall 4 (8800 N_{gg}).

In order to eventually train a neural network to detect percent difference from the surge line, the intermediate goal

was to train the network to detect mass flow, \dot{M} . Since pressure ratio is already available using existing engine sensors, mass flow would allow the reconstruction of the compressor map for a given compressor efficiency.

Mass flow training data was obtained by employing a compressor map model (see Simulink model shown in Figure 2) developed by Impact Technologies. Data from this test was entered into the model, and corresponding mass flow values were obtained. As shown in Figure 3, these mass flow values do not follow expected trends for varying VSV angle and corresponding Pr increase. Mass flow should be reduced, at least slightly, when vane angle is increased. It was therefore determined that, since this

¹ “U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright.”

² IEEEAC paper #1001, Version 6, Updated August 11, 2004

model's look-up table (which has only corrected N_{gg} and power turbine speed, N_{pt} , as inputs) was constructed using typical engine VSV set points, it was not suitable for off-design VSV data.

The existing compressor map for the CF6 engine (from which the LM2500 is an aero-derivative) was therefore manually entered into a look-up table. Figure 4 shows the

Simulink model developed for this purpose. Data obtained during testing was entered into the model and a corresponding mass flow output was obtained. As shown in Figure 5, mass flow values respond as expected for varying VSV angle. The change in mass flow versus pressure ratio is more pronounced at higher speeds, which is also consistent with the compressor map.

Figure 1^[1]

Figure 2 – Impact Tech. Simulink Compressor Model

Figure 3

Figure 4 – Simulink Compressor Map Model

Figure 5

Neural Network Modeling

Network Setup

Once the Simulink model was developed for outputting mass flow, neural network input parameters were chosen.

The Matlab Neural Network Toolbox was utilized for this effort. The multi-layer perceptron network specified,^[2] which contained 2 layers as shown in Figure 6, employed a non-linear sigmoidal function for summing at each node. Figure 6 also shows the engine operating parameters initially chosen as neural network inputs.

Figure 6

Training with On-Design “Map” Data (8 engine input parameters)

The network was trained first on steady, on-design VSV data. The goal of this effort was to determine if such a network could be extended to accurately output mass flow for off-design data having only knowledge of the typical on-design operation of the engine. This would be advantageous should the network be employed in a situation where VSV calibration is in question.

Figure 7 shows the training results for the network, performance goal was 0. As shown, the network performance at 1200 epochs is $1.61419e-007$. Figure 8 shows the output of the network versus the mass flow as calculated by the Simulink model. As shown in Figure 8, the network did not perform acceptably for off-design data.

Training with Off-Design “Map” Data (8 engine input parameters)

Since the on-design-trained neural network did not perform acceptably when simulated with off-design data, the next step was to train the network with both on and off-design data. An identical network structure was chosen to that of Figure 6. Figure 9 shows the network when simulated with data from the LBES Stall 1. As shown, the network did not track well when compared to the CF6 map model. In order to determine which of the 8 parameters might be causing the drastic inaccuracy in mass flow for steady, on-design VSV (data points 600 through 2000 in Figure 9), data from the “Map” portion of the test was compared to that of the “Stall 1” portion. In addition, the neural network was simulated with each of the 8 parameters being varied by 20% and corresponding weight factors were developed. Table 1 shows that inlet air temperature has the greatest effect on the mass flow output in this case, but that gas generator speed is weighted the heaviest by the network in general.

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Table 1

	N_{gg}	N_{pt}	T₂	T₅₄	P_{t2}	P₅₄	P_{t3}	VSV Feedback
Map Data	6997	989	80.195	912	14.6	18.5	53.891	16.098
Stall 1 Data	6999	887	95.695	935	14.5	18.098	51.688	15
% change	-0.03%	10.87%	-17.62%	-2.49%	0.69%	2.20%	4.17%	7.06%
NN Weight Factors	2.05	0.07	0.40	0.54	1.74	0.01	0.12	0.08
Overall Effect	-0.00059	0.0081	-0.0704	-0.013	0.012	0.0002	0.0051	0.005889997

Training with Simplified “Map” Data (2 calculated engine inputs)

Although initially, several parameters were selected as inputs to the neural network in order to allow for the largest amount of information from which to train, this approach appeared to be unsuccessful. A new, streamlined approach was therefore chosen. It was decided to limit the neural network inputs to only those employed by the Simulink

compressor map model. Inputs were limited to corrected gas generator speed and calculated compressor pressure ratio. The structure chosen was a 2-layer ML perceptron network with a 2-5-2-1 node structure. Log-sigmoidal, Tan-sigmoidal, and purely linear neural network nodes were selected. Tan-sigmoidal did not train with a variation of less than 10^{-2} , and these results are therefore not shown. Log-sigmoidal and purely linear results are compared to the CF6 Simulink model outputs in Figure 10.

Figure 10

As shown, the mass flow values from the sigmoidal, 2-input neural network track exceptionally well in the range where the 8-input neural network did not. Once VSV angle is varied above a certain level, the network no longer tracks along with the CF6 map. This is most likely due to the fact that the network was never trained on data with VSV angles and corresponding pressure ratios of this magnitude.

Training with Combination “Map”, Stall1 and Stall2 Data (2 calculated engine inputs)

Since, as seen in Figure 10, the neural network trained using data from the “Map” test could not be transitioned to track actual stall events during stalls 1 and 2, the next step was to train the neural network using a combination of “Map” data and data from stalls 1 and 2. The goal of this effort was to “build-in” understanding of the nuances of stall events in general. A 2-layer network with a 2-4-3-1 node structure was utilized. Figure 11 shows the results of the training. As shown, the network tracked the entire training set quite well. However, this network still did not quite capture the downward trend exhibited in stall 3 as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 11

Figure 12

It became apparent that, although zero values were entered into the CF6 look-up tables in order to accurately simulate

flow separation, these zero values were causing improper interpolation at operating points near, but to the right of the

surge line. This explained and somewhat negated the accuracy of the rapid downward trend in mass flow during stall events.

Further research into gas turbine compressor performance modeling yielded a potential solution to greatly improve the CF6 Simulink model. In order to generate compressor map look-up tables, an approach is often used in which lines parallel to the surge line (known as Beta lines) are plotted. An intermediate Beta versus N_{ggr} look-up table is generated through which more accurate mass flow and also compressor efficiency versus Beta tables are generated.

Since beta runs parallel to the surge line, the Beta values for a given engine state were used as a measure of stall margin. In fact Beta lines with a value less than one were utilized, as shown in Figure 13, to represent a condition where the engine was stalled and mass flow values must be ignored. Using this technique, zero values in the mass flow values to the left of the surge line were replaced with smoother, more continuous values. These values, while meaningless in the presence of beta less than unity, allowed for more realistic interpolation to the right of the surge line (Beta greater than unity).

Figure 13 shows the compressor map overlaid with lines of constant Beta. This map was utilized to generate a new CF6 Simulink model.

Figure 13^[3]

Figure 14

Comparison of mass flow output from the previous CF6 Simulink model and new CF6/Beta model is shown in Figure 14. As shown in the Stall 1 data, the mass flow values generated by the Beta model, unlike the original CF6 model, did not have a pronounced downward trend during stall.

Figures 15 and 16 show Beta values overlaid with Nggr for Stalls 1 and 2 respectively. As shown, stall, and corresponding emergency engine shutdown, coincides well with beta equal to unity.

Figure 15

Figure 16

Figure 17

Figure 18

The two-input network was then modified to output both Beta and mass flow. This network did not converge well during training. An additional layer of nodes was added, resulting in a 2-4-8-4-2 structure. Figure 17 shows the training results for this network after 10000 epochs. Figure 18 shows that the trends from this network agreed with the outputs from the Simulink CF6/Beta Model when the network was simulated with Stall3 data. Therefore, the end result was a neural network that accurately outputs mass flow for steady-state engine operations while also outputting an indicator, beta, for the user to disregard mass flow at the actual onset of stall. This network fulfilled the end goal of outputting a stall margin for the LM2500 engine. It can eventually be used, in an overall algorithm to safely operate the LM2500 engine closer to the stall line in order to improve fuel efficiency.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The initial 8-2-1 neural network implementation did not provide expected output. This was due to an overload of input data into the neural network. When the network was reduced to a 2-4-8-4-2 structure with parallel Beta lines, more accurate mass flow output was generated that mapped back to a known compressor map. The final outcome of

using a neural network to detect and output a compressor stall margin value and associated risk of compressor stall is achieved.

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BIOGRAPHY

Daniel Caguiat has been working for Naval Surface Warfare Center since 1997. He has a Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering from Drexel University and a Master of Science in Mechanical Engineering from University of Pennsylvania. His gas turbine work experience includes Automated Oil Analysis Systems, Online Water Wash Systems, Compressor Performance

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